

Anand: A Path Breaker Stylist

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Abstract:

Anand is a path breaker stylist. His narrative strategies, engages a reader and takes him to the realistic fictional world. He very often narrates the facts that help the reader to understand the plot better. He, being a seasoned stylist, he applies the narrative techniques to send his message loud and clear to the readers. This paper intends to explore the various narrative techniques of Anand.

Keywords: Stream of consciousness, reality, code-mixing, suffering, downtrodden.

Introduction:

Mulk Raj Anand was a social reformer who depicted the struggles and pains of the underprivileged in our society. He admits that although he creatively transforms the characters from his personal experience. He enriched the English language by introducing into its body a mix of the Punjabi and Hindustani elements. The protagonists experience emotional issues are subtly narrated with all delicacies of life.

Stylistic Devices

Anand believed that the writer's purpose was to communicate in simple, natural, and direct prose. He was against artificiality. In most of the novels he used third person narrative which helps him probe into the intricacies of the character. In the **Big Heart** novel, he uses third person narrative to depict one day in Ananta's life. It makes Ananta's life and death more intense. In the **Private life of an Indian Prince** novel, he uses first person narrative. In this novel he describes personal grief. In the **Barber's Trade Union** reflects the old narrative tradition around which Anand grew up.

(A) Reality:

Anand uses realism to highlight a number of significant indicators, including caste, status, circumstances, etc. He stood up for the underprivileged and those who were abused. A lot of things in life are considered to be in the grey area and aren't discussed much, but this writer broke this rule and did. The audience is able to comprehend characters due to the detailed description. Using imagery, adjectives, sound effects, and ritual descriptions in many sentences helps to make the story seem more real. In his novel *Untouchable* he describes Bakha who picks up filth to keep the surrounding clean. He starts with the description of a colony situated in Bulashah. The realistic portrayal of the house, landfills and the condition of the outcast colony has been realistically portrayed by Anand. The picture of the outcast has been realistically portrayed because of the situation of the slums situated in the towns and cities in India which

any reader can relate to as it is still prevalent in India. In this novel he depicts the conflict of the downtrodden using the character Bakha. Bakha wants to live the life of Tommies or soldiers who treat him humanely. He tells us how the caste system was prevailing in 1930's and 1940's in India. Sohini needed to wait near the well to get water as downtrodden were not to touch well. Bakha wished to enter the temple but the underprivileged were not allowed to enter.

(B) Internal Point Of View:

Anand uses the internal point of view to depict all his themes. Viewing of events from the character's eye is called an internal point of view.

Anand presents the theme in *Untouchable* through Bakha's perspective. From Bakha's perspective, the outcast colony is described. The focus of the story veers slightly away from Bakha when discussing the Bakha home. The point of view at Coolie is not far from Munoo. He strives to convey the social rage he portrays in both of his novels. The reader's eyes are filled with emotions as they read about Munoo's unfortunate past. It is notable how the author depicts the character's inner thoughts and feelings.

(C) Stream Of Consciousness:

Untouchable and *The Big Heart* both these novels represent one day of the protagonist's life but shift in thought. The entire book is written in Bakha's stream of consciousness. He employs a dream scenario in which Bakha imagines himself in a city, perched on top of a train, which starts moving out of nowhere while he is terrified. He is then moved to a different location.

(D) Dream, Fantasies And Illusions:

This structure plays a significant role in Anand's storytelling. Similar to how he did while describing a day in Bakha's life, he employs the approach of alternating nice and painful. The difficult life Bakha leads is mixed with tiny illusions, such as Bakha's want to appear like Sahib and stroll alongside Chota. In larger cities like Bombay, Coolie Munoo has an impression of luxury

and prosperity. The dream and fancies break the narrative's monotony and provide readers a peek into the character's inner thoughts.

(E)Speech Variation:

In Anand works speech of the upper class is different from the untouchables and other castes of the society. He constantly mixes 'boli basha' with Indian English to show the reality of the situation. He constantly mixes words not only from Hindi and Punjabi but also from French, German and Urdu. In Untouchable Gulabo abuses Sohini

"Ari bitch! Do you take me for a buffoon?"

When Colonel George directs Munoo to church saying,

"Ither! Ither" (Untouchable 10)

Another speech variations are depicted through the translation of the 'emotion' in the sentence. Such sentences can be easily differentiated due to peculiar ways of expressing emotions.

(F)Sentences:

In every novel the type of sentence used by the characters are different. It depends on the background, education, culture, class and caste. In Anand's novels, interrogative language is not frequently used. Anand has used rhetorical questions in his earlier writings. The author employs hyperbole and long, repeated words in Untouchable and Coolie. He attempts to tell the truth by using repetitious words. Just as Bakha ponders, "What can we do? We are outcasts?" He frequently utilizes exclamatory marks. Exclamatory marks are used in Hindi and Punjabi writing to emphasize strong feelings. The issue is made more realistic by the employment of narrative style. Since the majority of illiterates have a restricted vocabulary, including an exclamation point makes the statement's tone more clear to the reader.

His use of both long and short sentences demonstrates how well he understands the language. Another factor is that many characters are illiterate, which causes them to utilize simple language, whereas educated characters employ complex sentences. He translated dialogues from Punjabi and Hindi.

(G)Coinage:

He held that the mother tongue's original vibration gave authenticity to the speech's contents. So many hybrid compounds were created as a result of his linguistic experiments. 'Double' combined with the hindi word 'roti', to make a hybrid 'Double-roti' a popular synonym for 'bread'. Some other words that are used by Anand are goras, bania, pundit, jalebis, hakim, bhangi, chota babu, chaprasi. He adds an Indian touch to his words.

(H) Ellipses:

The character is unable to communicate, and this is a new way to use ellipses to emphasize their desperation. Like Lalu's pathetic monologue after hair-cut, Bakha's emotional outburst after the touching incident. These ellipses indicate the pain the character is undergoing.

Conclusion:

Anand's narrative pattern is intended to explore the emotions of his characters. Furthermore, it is indisputable that Anand is responsible for moulding the character and adding colour with his pen. One may quickly understand the Anand's narrative because it is clear and concise. The reader can feel the feelings that the characters are going through. His style is simple, innovative that enthalls the reader and creates an indelible impression

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